

Developing a Naming, Folder, and Metadata Structure for a Large Multimodal Research Dataset

1. Purpose and scope

This report documents data stewardship support for a large multimodal research project (Big Mouse Data - Designing "natural" tasks from a mouse-centric perspective; https://www.scienceofintelligence.de/research-projects/project_40/) from the Cluster of Excellence "Science of Intelligence" (<https://www.scienceofintelligence.de/>). The data stewardship support was provided to the cluster as part of the BUA funded project CARDS (Collaboratively Advancing Research Data Support, <https://www.bihealth.org/de/aktuell/cards>).

The support focused on improving the organisation, documentation, and future interpretability of heterogeneous project data. The main outputs were a revised naming and folder structure, machine-readable context files that link each recording date to related files stored elsewhere in the project structure, and a relational database schema for structured metadata management.

2. Background and RDM challenge

The project generates heterogeneous data from several sources. These include audio and video recordings, RFID-derived data, environmental measurements, physiological and scoring data, setup-related information, and project documentation. The data streams differ in file format, data volume, temporal structure, recording frequency, storage location, and documentation practice.

The initial data organisation reflected the practical needs of active research. Some files were generated automatically by recording software or devices, some were exported from instruments, some were copied from removable storage media, and some were maintained manually in spreadsheets or laboratory documentation. Data was stored across different systems, including recording computers, external hard drives, network-attached storage, and institutional cloud storage.

This situation is common in complex research projects and does not necessarily hamper day-to-day work. However, it creates risks for long-term interpretation, transfer, and reuse, and may increase the risk of data loss during handover or storage transitions. If file names, folder structures, and contextual information are based mainly on local habits or individual knowledge, later users may find it difficult to understand which files belong together, which time period they cover, where the authoritative copy is stored, and how recordings relate to contextual measurements.

The data stewardship support therefore focused on organising the data according to explicit, consistent, and machine-readable principles.

3. Revised naming and folder structure

A revised naming and folder structure was developed to organise the dataset by recording date, data modality, and contextual period. The structure separates daily recording data from contextual files that may be collected, exported, or updated at different intervals.

A simplified version of the revised structure is shown below:

- BMD_data
 - o **YYYY-MM-DD**
 - Audio_data
 - Ch1
 - o „YYYY-MM-DD_T0000001.wav“ ... „YYYY-MM-DD_T0000259.wav“
 - ...
 - Video_data
 - YYYY-MM-DD_HH-mm_Modulecode.avi
 - YYYY-MM-DD_context.json
 - o **YYYY-Www**
 - **YYYY-Www**_Gewichte_und_Scores.xlsx
 - **YYYY-MM-DD_roomnumber**.dbf
 - **YYYY-MM-DD_HH-mm_ID**_Microcontroller.csv

YYYY-MM-DD_context.json:

```
{
  "physio": "../YYYY-Www/YYYY-Www_Gewichte_und_Scores.xlsx",
  "env": "../YYYY-Www/YYYY-MM-DD_roomnumber.dbf"
  "rfid": "../YYYY-Www/YYYY-MM-DD_HH-mm_ID_Microcontroller.csv"
}
```

The date-based folders are used for files directly associated with a specific recording date, especially audio and video data. Audio files are further organised by channel, reflecting the recording setup. Video file names include date, time, and module information.

The week-based folders contain contextual or supplementary files that are recorded, exported, or read out on a weekly basis. This includes measurement tables, environmental data logger exports, and RFID-related files.

The naming convention uses ISO-formatted dates (YYYY-MM-DD) and avoids spaces or special characters. This improves chronological sorting, reduces ambiguity, and supports later automated parsing or database import.

4. Context files

A key design decision was the introduction of date-specific context files. These files link daily recording folders to related contextual data stored elsewhere in the project structure. At the beginning, these files were generated manually, but this task can be automated later on.

The context file acts as a lightweight, machine-readable bridge between recording data and contextual information. This is useful because not all relevant data are generated at the same frequency or stored in the same folder. The context files also provide a practical basis for later automated ingestion into the metadata database.

5. Metadata database schema

After the naming and folder structure had been defined, a relational metadata database schema was developed. The database functions as a metadata registry that documents which files exist, which time periods they cover, where they are stored, and how they relate to subjects, events, measurements, devices, and data modalities.

The schema includes core tables for subjects or animals, time ranges, events, event types, audio files, video files, RFID files, environmental files, and measurements. It also includes relationship tables linking subjects (animals) to events, audio files, and video files. This structure allows the project to represent many-to-many relationships, for example when one event relates to several files or one recording contains information relevant to several subjects or events.

The modality-specific file tables capture relevant technical metadata. For example, video file metadata include file name, camera, time range, storage location, file size, frame rate, resolution, and codec. Audio file metadata include file name, microphone, time range, storage location, and file size. RFID and environmental files are represented in separate tables linked to time ranges and storage locations.

The tables include provenance fields such as *created_by*, *created_at*, *last_updated*, and *updated_by*. These fields support traceability and help document the curation of metadata during the project period.

6. Planned metadata publication and hosting

The next planned step is to deploy the metadata database on a local NAS server that is not connected to the internet and is only accessible from inside the lab. It is planned in the project to publish regular metadata dumps on Zenodo. Each metadata dump would represent a snapshot of the database at a specific point in time. A weekly publication interval is currently planned.

7. Conclusion

This report describes data stewardship support for a large multimodal research dataset. The work transformed an initially heterogeneous and partly person-dependent data organisation into a more structured framework based on three layers: a consistent naming convention, a date- and modality-based folder structure, and a relational metadata

database schema. The approach improves the interpretability and manageability of the dataset during the project period and prepares the ground for future metadata publication.

At the time of writing, the metadata database hosting and Zenodo publication workflow are still in preparation. Once implemented, the planned workflow will allow the project team to publish regular metadata dumps as versions of a single Zenodo record. This will provide a transparent and citable record of the evolving metadata while keeping access to the underlying research data subject to separate project-specific governance decisions.